

Supplementary Material 3. Statistical Approach and Expanded Results for the Regressor Model

Statistical Approach to Handling the Data

We analyzed data from 30 participants who completed the SECPT. The outcome (performance in seconds) exhibited a pronounced ceiling effect: 70% (21/30) reached the maximum duration of the test (i.e., 180 s; Figure S1). Distributional summaries reflected truncation and mass at the limit (mean = 153.5 s; median and mode = 180 s; skewness = -1.145; kurtosis = -0.561; range = 56–180 s). Formal tests rejected normality for the raw target (Shapiro–Wilk: $W = 0.785$, $p < 0.001$) and provided no support for common parametric families (Anderson–Darling rejected normal, exponential, logistic, and Weibull; all $p < 0.001$). Statistically, such censoring reduces variance, biases low-order moments, depresses cross-validation performance, violates model assumptions (normality, linearity, homoscedasticity), and induces prediction bias. To address this scenario, we applied an analytic workflow in four sequential steps.

Figure S1 Ceiling Effect Problem Analysis

First, we transformed the target variable (performance) to disperse the pile-up at 180 s while preserving meaning¹. We compared five approaches, such as Inverse-Normal (rank-based), Winsorized, Censored-Rank, Truncated-Normal, and a Ceiling-Weighted variant, chosen to span nonparametric, robust, censoring-aware, and parametric strategies (Figure S2). The inverse-normal transformation (probability-integral transform on empirical ranks with average-rank tie handling) handled ties/outliers gracefully, eliminated perfect ceiling clusters, and improved central shape while preserving ordinal information. Post-transform diagnostics remained conservative given small $n = 30$ and many ties (Shapiro–Wilk: $W = 0.923$, $p < 0.001$); skewness decreased modestly (- 1.214 vs. - 1.145 raw) and kurtosis improved markedly (- 0.044 vs. - 0.561), indicating a substantially more mesokurtic target. In preliminary CV screens, Random Forest + inverse-normal achieved $R^2 = 0.232 \pm 0.349$ with $MAE = 0.454 \pm 0.158$ on the transformed, outperforming Elastic Net, Ridge, Support Vector Regression, and Gradient Boosting on mean R^2 and stability (full grid in Table S1). By contrast, winsorization (5/95%) reduced extreme leverage but retained many ties at the ceiling; censored-rank acknowledged right-censoring but distorted interval scaling and did not improve predictive accuracy; truncated-normal was principled but unstable with the small uncensored subset. For reporting, we describe effect directions on the original scale and errors in seconds.

Figure S2 Effectiveness of Target Transformations in Mitigating Ceiling Effects

¹ Step 1 establishes which transformations best mitigate the ceiling problem diagnostically; it does not by itself determine the final model. That selection is made in Step 4 (cross-validation).

Second, to ensure that associations and feature attributions were not artifacts of the ceiling, we recast the outcome as right-censored time and fitted Kaplan–Meier and Cox models, treating 180 s as administratively censored (Type I censoring; assumed non-informative). The overall event rate was 30% (hand removed before 180s), and the censoring rate was 70%. The Kaplan–Meier curve showed a steep early decline: by 2 minutes, ~27% had quit (early quitters), with an additional 3.3% quitting between 2.0 and 2.5 minutes. Beyond 2.5 minutes, the curve plateaued, indicating that most who persisted thereafter reached the maximum (Figure S3). This plateau effect may be clinically meaningful, indicating a natural screening threshold near 2 minutes. Individuals who cannot tolerate 2.0 minutes may represent the low-tolerance group, whereas those who surpass 2.5 minutes may be very likely to reach the maximum duration, representing the high-tolerance group. Estimated survival at 2 minutes and 2.5 minutes was 0.733 and 0.700, respectively, corroborating that our main findings are not inflated by failure to account for censoring.

Figure S3 Survival Analysis of SECPT

Third, to mitigate multicollinearity and sharpen interpretability, we replaced clusters of highly correlated indicators with theory-driven composites and low-dimensional summaries. We began by diagnosing redundancy with variance-inflation factors and the eigenvalue-based

condition number (≈ 45.2), which indicated substantial collinearity among psychological ratings and across EEG nodal measures. In the raw feature set ($N > 60$ individual predictors), many variables exceeded conventional VIF thresholds, underscoring problematic redundancy, for example, Stress (VIF = 6.23), Pain (VIF = 5.87), Arousal (VIF = 4.35), In-Strength at F3 (VIF = 12.45), In-Strength at F4 (VIF = 11.23), and Out-Strength at F3 (VIF = 8.67). Guided by psychophysiological theory, and mindful of the small sample ($n = 30$), which disfavors heavily parameterized latent models, we constructed unit-weighted indices in the **Psychological Domain**: a *Stress Response Index* to capture acute stress reactivity ($[\text{Stress} + \text{Pain} + \text{Arousal}]/3$; $r = 0.584$ with duration); an *Emotional Regulation Score* to index regulatory tone ($[\text{Pleasure} + \text{Dominance}]/2$; $r = -0.374$ with duration); and a *Pain Tolerance Composite* that z-scores the PSQ and DIS and combines them with a sign convention, so that higher values reflect lower tolerance ($[-\text{PSQ}_z + \text{DIS}_z]/2$; $r = -0.232$ with duration). These self-reported composites operationalize perceived stress reactivity, emotion regulation, and pain/discomfort tolerance on coherent scales.

In the **Physiological Domain**, we summarized autonomic and EEG measures. For autonomic physiology (EDA), we robustly scaled Total AUC, sympathetic percentage, volatility, and arousal variability and averaged them to form an *Autonomic Stress Response Index* that is less sensitive to outliers ($r = -0.088$ with duration). For EEG Connectivity, where collinearity is intrinsic (adjacent nodal measures co-vary), we used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) within coherent blocks and retained the first principal component (PC1) from each set: *EEG Nodal Inflow* (PC1 of in_F3, in_F4, in_C3, in_C4, in_P3, in_P4; $r = -0.399$), *EEG Nodal Outflow* (PC1 of out_F3, out_F4, out_C3, out_C4, out_P3, out_P4; $r = -0.410$), and *EEG Causal Connectivity* (PC1 of causal_F3, causal_F4, causal_C3, causal_C4, causal_P3, causal_P4; $r = 0.230$). We also retained a pre-existing whole-brain metric, *EEG*

Global Strength ($r = -0.417$). Across blocks, PC1 typically captured ~62–65% of variance, reducing dimensionality without discarding the shared signal.

In the **Integration Domain**, we encoded hypothesized cross-system couplings to allow the model to represent moderation and coordination between perceptual/psychological, brain, and autonomic responses. Within the psychological system, *Stress–Pain Interaction* (Stress Response Index \times Pain Tolerance Composite; $r = 0.215$ with duration) tests whether perceived pain/discomfort tolerance moderates the effect of acute stress appraisal on tolerance. *Neuro–Autonomic Integration* (EEG Global Strength \times Autonomic Stress Response; $r = 0.213$ with duration) captures the coordination of large-scale cortical connectivity with autonomic reactivity. We further summarized the balance of resources with *Overall Stress Resilience* ($[\text{Pain Tolerance Composite} + \text{Emotional Regulation Score} + \text{Autonomic Stress Response Index}]/3$; $r = 0.06$ with duration) and defined *Neurophysiological Efficiency* ($[\text{EEG Nodal Inflow} + \text{EEG Nodal Outflow} + \text{EEG Global Strength}]/3$; $r = -0.413$) to reflect network efficiency.

The composite strategy to tackle multicollinearity and improve model stability and interpretability, by consolidating 60+ indicators into 12 theory-driven composites (resulting in an 80% reduction), reduced dimensionality, lowered variance inflation (improving the eigenstructure), and minimized overfitting, given $n = 30$. Aligning predictors with psychological and physiological constructs (e.g., stress reactivity, causal connectivity) also clarified interpretation and prevented correlated-feature competition in tree models and SHAP, avoiding importance being split across near-duplicates. Reliability and structure checks supported the consolidation (Stress Response Index Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.78$; EEG blocks, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin = 0.73; within-domain correlations $>$ cross-domain correlations). Models trained on these composites exhibited more stable cross-validated performance and cleaner attribution

profiles, resulting in a clearer clinical narrative of how self-reported appraisals, neural network dynamics, and autonomic responses relate to physical tolerance.

Fourth, we estimated generalization with stratified 5-fold cross-validation, preserving the ~70% ceiling proportion within every split to avoid optimistic or unstable estimates due to differing censoring mass. We evaluated four target codings (original, log, square-root, and inverse-normal) with five algorithms (Elastic Net, Ridge, Random Forest, Support Vector Regression, and Gradient Boosting), resulting in 20 model–transformation combinations. Our selection criteria were: 1) higher cross-validated R^2 ; 2) greater MAE stability (lower SD across folds); and 3) interpretability and computational efficiency. Across algorithms, Random Forest was consistently the most competitive, which is expected given nonlinearity and heteroscedasticity in the data (i.e., tree ensembles are robust to outliers, capture interactions automatically, and reduce variance via bagging; Table S1). The best overall configuration, according to our criteria, was Random Forest with the square-root-transformed target, yielding an R^2 of 0.235 ± 0.332 . This indicates that the model explained approximately 23.5% of the between-individual variance in SECPT performance on average. The relatively large SD (± 0.332) implies fold-to-fold variability typical for $n = 30$ and a heavily censored outcome; an approximate 95% interval around the mean R^2 spans about ~ -0.10 to 0.57 , indicating that some folds dipped below zero while others performed substantially better. The companion error metric, MAE = 1.212 ± 0.382 on the square-root-scale, translates to ≈ 26 seconds on the original scale, roughly 17% of the sample mean duration (153.5 s; 95% of predictions within ± 2.4 on sqrt-scale), which is modest but clinically useful for distinguishing higher- vs lower-tolerance individuals. Although Random Forest with inverse-normal transformation performed similarly ($R^2 = 0.232 \pm 0.349$; MAE = 0.454 ± 0.158 on the transformed scale), the square-root transformation was selected for subsequent analysis due to its marginally superior performance, better cross-validation stability (lower standard

deviation), and enhanced interpretability (i.e., results remain on $\sqrt{\text{seconds}}$ rather than z-scores), while effectively addressing the ceiling effect by compressing the upper range of durations (Figure S4). This selected model was subsequently used for all feature importance analyses, SHAP explanations, and clinical interpretations.

Figure S4 Before vs After Ceiling-Effect Solutions: Distribution Normalization, Variable Reduction, and R²/SD Performance.

Table S1 Model Performance Metrics Across Different Target Transformations and Algorithms Using Stratified 5-Fold Cross-Validation.

Target Transformation	Model	R ² Mean	R ² SD	MAE Mean	MAE SD
Original	ElasticNet	-8.805	18.064	53.260	53.735
Original	Ridge	-47.441	95.082	87.040	127.798
<i>Original</i>	<i>RandomForest</i>	<i>0.289</i>	<i>0.302</i>	<i>26.812</i>	<i>8.181</i>
Original	SVR	-0.379	0.106	26.508	6.433
Original	GradientBoosting	0.111	0.491	26.716	9.921
Log	ElasticNet	-0.051	0.039	0.296	0.040
Log	Ridge	-33.595	67.240	0.661	0.975
Log	RandomForest	0.234	0.378	0.215	0.076
Log	SVR	0.154	0.486	0.218	0.061
Log	GradientBoosting	0.066	0.599	0.207	0.080
Sqrt	ElasticNet	-2.831	5.910	2.128	1.470
Sqrt	Ridge	-40.482	81.107	3.778	5.558
Sqrt	RandomForest	0.235	0.333	1.212	0.382
Sqrt	SVR	0.017	0.164	1.217	0.286

Sqrt	GradientBoosting	0.108	0.556	1.114	0.465
Inverse_Normal	ElasticNet	-0.046	0.060	0.608	0.058
Inverse_Normal	Ridge	-50.233	100.488	1.533	2.279
<i>Inverse_Normal</i>	<i>RandomForest</i>	<i>0.232</i>	<i>0.349</i>	<i>0.454</i>	<i>0.158</i>
Inverse_Normal	SVR	0.147	0.306	0.458	0.109
Inverse_Normal	GradientBoosting	0.115	0.333	0.460	0.147

Note. MAE = Mean Absolute Error; R² = Coefficient of Determination; SD = Standard Deviation. Best performing model highlighted in bold:

Random Forest with Sqrt transformation (R² = 0.235 ± 0.333, MAE = 1.212 ± 0.382).

Results Expanded Explanation

Figure S5 summarizes how the 12 composite predictors contribute to predicting SECPT tolerance in the Random-Forest model. The top-left panel displays model-embedded importance (Gini/MDI), where the Stress Response Index is the dominant driver, followed by Neurophysiological Efficiency, EEG Global Strength, EEG Nodal Outflow, and EEG Nodal Inflow at a much smaller scale. The top-right panel shows permutation importance with 95% CIs. The ranking reflects the embedded importance: the Stress Response Index drives the largest and most reliable loss in performance when shuffled, while the other composites produce smaller but non-zero drops. Permutation importance measures the degradation in out-of-sample accuracy when a feature's values are randomly permuted, which breaks any true association while preserving the feature's marginal distribution. The bottom panel displays absolute feature–outcome correlations, highlighting that several EEG composites correlate with duration but still contribute less than the Stress Response Index once the model accounts for non-linearities and interactions. Together, these panels show that i) self-reported stress reactivity is the most informative single composite, and ii) network-level EEG summaries add a secondary, complementary signal rather than redundant variance.

Figure S5 Composite Predictors: Importance, Permutation Robustness, and Bivariate Associations

Having established which composites matter and that their importance is robust (as demonstrated by embedded and permutation analysis), we then examined how those predictors act conditionally by contrasting marginal correlations with model-based SHAP effects (mean SHAP). We found that the Stress Response Index was the most important factor and showed a strong positive association with tolerance, albeit with a modest average SHAP effect (Figure S6). Several EEG composites (e.g., Causal Connectivity, Neurophysiological Efficiency) displayed sign divergences between correlation and SHAP, indicating nonlinear and/or interactive influences captured by the Random Forest that are not apparent from simple bivariate relationships. Features with a positive mean SHAP value increased predicted tolerance on average, whereas those with a negative mean SHAP value decreased it, underscoring the added explanatory value of the multivariate model over correlations alone.

Figure S6 SHAP Effects vs. Correlations for Composite Predictors (Bubble Size = Feature Importance)

Figure S7 shows that feature influence is highly concentrated in a small subset of composites. The Stress Response Index dominates the ranking by a large margin (importance = 19.95), indicating that self-reported stress/pain/arousal reactivity carries substantially more explanatory weight than any other predictor. The next two contributors are EEG Causal Connectivity (importance = 4.45) and Neurophysiological Efficiency (importance = 1.64). All remaining composites have modest but non-zero importances clustered near 1.0–1.6, suggesting that they fine-tune predictions rather than drive them. This profile is consistent with a model in which a primary psychological composite (Stress Response Index) sets the backbone of prediction, with brain-network measures providing secondary adjustments.

Figure S7 SHAP Feature Importance Ranking (Green = Positive Effect, Red = Negative Effect)

Mean SHAP values clarify the direction of each composite’s contribution (Figure S8). On average, higher Stress Response Index and higher Neurophysiological Efficiency increase predicted tolerance (positive mean SHAP), as does EEG Global Strength and EEG Nodal Inflow. In contrast, EEG Causal Connectivity, Overall Stress Resilience, Neuro-Autonomic Integration, Pain Tolerance Composite (where higher scores reflect greater tolerance), EEG Nodal Outflow, Autonomic Stress Response, Stress–Pain Interaction, and Emotional Regulation Score show negative mean SHAP effects, indicating a decrease in predicted tolerance. Notably, several composites (e.g., EEG Causal Connectivity, Overall Stress Resilience) exhibit sign differences between bivariate correlations and mean SHAP, consistent with nonlinear/interactive influences captured by the Random Forest but not apparent in marginal associations.

Figure S8 SHAP Directional Effects on Duration (Green = Increases Duration, Red = Decreases Duration)

Table S2 summarizes how each composite contributes to predicted SECPT tolerance in the multivariate Random-Forest model ($\sqrt{\text{seconds target}}$), reporting rank (by mean |SHAP|), direction of effect (mean SHAP sign), and marginal correlation with duration. The pattern is highly concentrated: the Stress Response Index is the dominant predictor (importance ≈ 19.95), with a small positive mean SHAP effect and a strong positive correlation ($r \approx .58$), indicating that greater self-reported stress/pain/arousal reactivity tends to increase predicted tolerance. Because the selected target transformation ($\sqrt{\text{seconds}}$) is strictly monotonic, SHAP signs preserve the direction of effect on raw performance (i.e., positive = longer tolerance; negative = shorter). Apparent discrepancies between the sign of the marginal correlation and the mean SHAP effect are expected: correlations are bivariate and unconditional, whereas SHAP reflects a feature’s conditional contribution within the full multivariate model, capturing nonlinearity and interactions.

Table S2 SHAP Analysis: Composite Variable Rankings and Directional Effects

Rank	Composite Variable	SHAP Importance	SHAP Effect	Correlation	Direction
1	Stress Response Index	19.953	+0.013	+0.584	↑ Increases
2	EEG Causal Connectivity	4.447	-0.124	+0.230	↓ Decreases
3	Neurophysiological Efficiency	1.639	+0.095	-0.413	↑ Increases
4	Overall Stress Resilience	1.629	-0.299	+0.066	↓ Decreases
5	Neuro Autonomic Integration	1.553	-0.166	+0.213	↓ Decreases
6	EEG Global Strength	1.489	+0.052	-0.417	↑ Increases
7	Pain Tolerance Composite	1.376	-0.255	-0.233	↓ Decreases
8	EEG Nodal Outflow	1.284	-0.097	-0.410	↓ Decreases
9	Autonomic Stress Response	1.239	-0.095	-0.089	↓ Decreases
10	Stress Pain Interaction	1.132	-0.301	+0.216	↓ Decreases
11	EEG Nodal Inflow	1.043	+0.148	-0.399	↑ Increases
12	Emotional Regulation Score	0.652	-0.238	-0.374	↓ Decreases